

Kinetics and Mechanism of Iridium(III) catalysed Oxidation of Aliphatic Amines by *N*-Bromosuccinimide

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Kinetics of Ir^{III} catalysed oxidation of primary aliphatic amines (ethylamine, n-propylamine and n-butylamine), secondary amine (diethylamine) and tertiary amine (triethylamine) by *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in perchloric acid medium and in presence of mercuric acetate have been studied. During a particular kinetic run the order of reaction in NBS is found to be unity. However, a decrease in the rate constant was observed with an increase in the initial NBS concentration. A near zero order dependence of rate with respect to substrate was observed. The rate is proportional to $\{k' + k''[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]\}$, where k' and k'' are the rate constants for uncatalysed and catalysed path respectively. The effect of acid is negligible in case of primary aliphatic amines while a retarding effect of acid was observed in case of diethylamine and triethylamine. The effect of $[\text{NaClO}_4]$ and $[\text{Succinimide}]$ on the rate of oxidation was negligible. A retarding effect of $[\text{acetic acid}]$ and $[\text{NaCl}]$ on the reaction rate has also been observed. A suitable mechanism consistent with the kinetic data has been proposed.

The transition metal ions have been widely used as catalysts in several redox-reactions^{1,2}. A few reports are available on the use of Ir^{III} as catalyst³. The oxidation of various organic compounds by *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS), which is a potent oxidant in acidic media, has been investigated⁴. The use of Ru^{III} as a catalyst in NBS oxidations has shown² involvement of several complexities like variation of order with respect to reactants, formation of various intermediates etc. In the present communication we report the result of iridium(III) catalysed oxidation of aliphatic amines by NBS.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The reaction mixtures containing a known excess of $[\text{NBS}]$ over $[\text{Amine}]$ were kept in presence of perchloric acid, mercuric acetate and iridiumtrichloride at 40° for 72 h. It was observed that one mole of substrate consumes 1, 2

an 3 moles of NBS in case of primary, secondary and tertiary amines respectively (Scheme 1). The formation of aldehyde as a product was confirmed by the m.p. of their 2-4 DNP derivatives.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [REACTANTS] ON RATE CONSTANTS AT 35°*

[NBS] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Amines] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Ir ^{III}] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	k ₁ (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)				
				Ethyl- amine	n-Propyl- amine	n-Butyl- amine	Diethyl- amine	Triethyl- amine
1.0	2.0	2.0	6.65	—	9.97	9.28	10.36	10.70
1.5	2.0	2.0	6.85	6.90	7.86	7.67	8.44	7.67
2.0	2.0	2.0	6.65	5.37	5.94	6.10	7.30	4.22
2.5	2.0	2.0	6.65	—	4.98	4.20	6.14	2.68
3.0	2.0	2.0	6.65	3.45	4.98	3.80	5.37	1.53
2.0	0.4	2.0	6.65	2.50	4.50	3.50	—	—
2.0	0.8	2.0	6.65	4.50	4.95	6.50	4.60	2.30
2.0	1.6	2.0	6.65	4.95	5.96	5.90	6.95	3.10
2.0	2.4	2.0	6.05	—	—	6.20	—	—
2.0	3.0	2.0	6.65	5.30	5.90	6.07	9.97	5.37
2.0	4.0	2.0	6.65	5.25	5.90	6.15	11.00	5.55
2.0	6.0	2.0	6.65	5.32	6.00	—	10.22	5.40
2.0	2.0	1.0	6.65	5.20	5.86	5.98	10.70	5.00
2.0	2.0	3.0	6.65	5.75	6.33	6.52	4.60	2.68
2.0	2.0	4.0	6.65	5.79	6.29	6.52	3.83	2.00
2.0	2.0	6.0	6.65	—	6.52	—	3.07	1.52
2.0	2.0	2.0	0.00	2.10	2.20	2.00	0.80	0.60
2.0	2.0	2.0	2.66	3.26	3.83	3.40	3.83	2.30
2.0	2.0	2.0	5.32	4.41	5.18	4.98	6.14	3.26
2.0	2.0	2.0	9.97	6.70	8.40	8.06	9.98	5.37
2.0	2.0	2.0	13.30	8.25	10.05	10.36	—	6.14
2.0	2.0	2.0	19.95	11.10	14.50	15.16	—	—

*[Hg(OAc)₂] = 10.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. The effect of $[\text{HClO}_4]$ was studied at a fixed ionic strength $\mu = 0.04 \text{ M}$.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [ACETIC ACID], [NaCl] AND [SUCCINIMIDE] ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS AT 35°*

[Acetic acid] % (v/v)	[NaCl] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[Succinimide] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> ₁ (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)				
			Ethyl- amine	n-propyl- amine	n-Butyl- amine	Diethyl- amine	Triethyl- amine
Nil	—	—	5.37	5.94	6.10	7.30	4.22
5.0	—	—	—	3.64	2.87	2.87	1.91
10.0	—	—	3.83	3.26	2.30	2.30	1.53
15.0	—	—	—	2.30	1.53	1.53	1.15
20.0	—	—	1.91	2.68	1.15	1.15	0.84
—	0.5	—	3.64	3.26	3.07	5.22	2.49
—	1.0	—	3.07	3.07	2.68	3.45	1.53
—	1.5	—	—	2.49	2.30	2.68	0.57
—	2.0	—	—	2.11	1.90	1.91	0.38
—	—	0.5	—	5.37	5.75	4.98	3.16
—	—	1.0	5.37	5.37	5.75	4.60	2.68
—	—	2.0	5.37	5.35	5.80	4.32	2.11
—	—	3.0	4.60	4.22	5.60	3.83	1.72

*[IrCl₂]=6.65 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄]=2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Amines]=2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NBS]=2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

TABLE 3—SALIENT FEATURES OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Observations	Results and conclusion
[NBS] effect : log [NBS] vs time plots are linear <i>k</i> _{obs} decreases with increase in [NBS] ₀	First order with respect to [NBS]
Substrate effect : <i>k</i> _{obs} increases with [substrate] at lower concentrations <i>k</i> _{obs} remains same at [substrate] > 2.0 × 10 ⁻³	First order with respect to [substrate] Zero order with respect to [substrate]
Catalyst effect : In absence of catalyst, IrCl ₂ In presence of catalyst IrCl ₂	The reactions are slow and showed first order dependence with respect to [NBS] Rate ∝ { <i>k</i> ' + <i>k</i> ''[IrCl ₂]}, where <i>k</i> ' and <i>k</i> '' are rate constants for uncatalysed and catalysed path respectively
Effect of [HClO₄] : In case of primary amines In case of secondary and tertiary amines	Negligible, rules out involvement of >NHBr ⁺ or protonated amine as reactive species Retarding, 1/ <i>k</i> _{obs} vs [HClO ₄] plots is a straight line with intercept
Effect of [succinimide] : In case of primary amine In case of secondary and tertiary amines	Negligible Retarding
Ionic strength effect :	Negligible in each case ; involvement of atleast a neutral molecule in rate determining step
Acetic acid effect :	Retarding (+ve dielectric effect) ; Anion-dipole or dipole-dipole interaction also rules out involvement of Br ⁺ in rate determining step
Cl⁻ effect :	Negative ; suggests IrCl ₂ as reactive species as IrCl ₂ in HCl exists as [IrCl ₂] ²⁻ [Ir(H ₂ O)Cl ₂] ²⁻ , [Ir(H ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂] ²⁻ [Ir(H ₂ O) ₃ Cl ₂] (Ref. 5)
Hg(OAc)₂ effect :	Negligible ; rules out its involvement in oxidation ; addition of mercuric acetate in reaction mixture completely mark the possibility of any oxidation by Br ₂ and ensure oxidation by NBS
Temp. effect : at 35, 40, 45 and 50°	<i>E</i> _{act} obtained from Arrhenius plots at 61.3, 61.3, 55.5, 32.5 and 38.3 kJ mol ⁻¹ for ethylamine, n-butylamine, n-propylamine, diethylamine and triethylamine respectively

In presence of Ir^{III}, the log[NBS] vs time plots were linear upto 85% of the reaction. Therefore pseudo-first order rate constants in NBS were calculated from the slopes of these plots for different system. The rate constants (k_{obs}) at different initial [reactants] are reported in Tables 1 and 2. An increase in initial [NBS] resulted in decrease in the k_{obs} (Table 1). The salient features of the results and the conclusion are summarised in Table 3.

On the basis of the results, a common mechanism for the oxidation of primary aliphatic amines by NBS in presence of Ir^{III} may be proposed as given in Chart 1. The rate of disappearance of NBS may be given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k_3[\text{Y}] \quad (1)$$

Again considering the total concentration of catalyst as

$$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{C}_1] + [\text{X}] + [\text{Y}] \quad (2)$$

where,

$$[\text{X}] = k_1[\text{S}][\text{C}_1] \quad (3)$$

and

$$[\text{Y}] = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{C}_1][\text{NBS}][\text{S}]}{\{k_3 + k_2[>\text{NH}]\}} \quad (4)$$

where, >NH represents succinimide. Thus finding [Y] in terms of total concentration of the catalyst, i.e. $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$, the rate law may be obtained as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_3 k_2 K_1 [\text{S}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{NBS}]}{\{k_3 + k_2[>\text{NH}]\}\{1 + K_1[\text{S}]\} + k_2 K_1 [\text{S}][\text{NBS}]} \quad (5)$$

Since step (iii) of Chart 1 is fast, $k_3 \gg k_2[>\text{NH}]$ may be taken as suitable approximation, and therefore equation (5) is converted into (6),

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_3 k_2 K_1 [\text{S}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{NBS}]}{k_3 \{1 + K_1[\text{S}]\} + k_2 K_1 [\text{S}][\text{NBS}]} \quad (6)$$

Further, at higher substrate concentrations, where $K_1[\text{S}] \gg 1$, the rate law (6) may be given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_3 k_2 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{NBS}]}{\{k_3 + k_2[\text{NBS}]\}} \quad (7)$$

which is in agreement with the experimental results for the oxidation of primary aliphatic amines.

The retarding effect of acid in case of secondary (diethylamine) and tertiary (triethylamine) amines may be explained on the basis an equilibrium (step ii, Chart 2) involving deprotonation of the complex between substrate and the catalyst. The total concentration of the catalyst at any time may be given as

$$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{C}_1] + [\text{X}'] + [\text{Y}'] + [\text{Z}] \quad (8)$$

where,

$$[\text{X}'] = K_1[\text{S}][\text{C}_1] \quad (9)$$

$$[\text{Y}'] = \frac{K_1[\text{X}']}{[\text{H}^+]} = K_1 K_2 [\text{S}][\text{C}_1]/[\text{H}^+] \quad (10)$$

and

$$[\text{Z}] = \frac{k_3 K_1 K_2 [\text{S}][\text{C}_1][\text{NBS}]}{\{k_3[>\text{NH}] + k_4\}[\text{H}^+]} \quad (11)$$

K_1 and K_2 also involve the water molecules. Also,

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k_4[\text{Z}] \quad (12)$$

Chart 1

Chart 2

Thus finding [Z] in terms of $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$, the rate law may be obtained as

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_4 k_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{S}] [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{NBS}]}{\{k_4 + k_3 [>\text{NH}]\} \{[\text{H}^+] (1 + K_1 [\text{S}]) + K_1 K_2 [\text{S}]\} + k_3 K_1 K_2 [\text{S}] [\text{NBS}]} \quad (13)$$

At higher substrate concentrations, where $K_1 [\text{S}] \gg 1$, the rate law (13) reduces to

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_4 k_2 K_2 [\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{NBS}]}{\{k_4 + k_3 [>\text{NH}]\} \{[\text{H}^+] + K_2\} + k_3 K_2 [\text{NBS}]} \quad (14)$$

In case of diethylamine and triethylamine it may be possible that the rate constants for steps (iii) and (iv) (Chart 2) are comparable, and thus $k_4 \gg k_3 [>\text{NH}]$ cannot be taken as suitable approximation. The rate law (14) explains zero-order dependence of rate on substrate, retarding effect of acid, succinimide and initial NBS concentration on the rate constant in case of secondary and tertiary amines.

Since the steps responsible for uncatalysed path are not included in the mechanism (Charts 1 and 2), the rate laws (6), (7), (13) and (14) do not show the intercepts obtained during the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$. The uncatalysed oxidation of n-butylamine by

NBS has been studied in detail. The results showed a first order dependence of rate with respect to each substrate and NBS and a negligible effect of acid on the rate constants.

Experimental

Ethylamine, n-butylamine, n-propylamine, diethylamine, triethylamine, iridiumtrichloride, N-bromosuccinimide, succinimide and mercuric acetate were of A.R. grade. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Solution of NBS was prepared fresh and its strength checked by iodometric method. Iridium trichloride was prepared in dilute HCl and stored in the dark. The strength of iridium trichloride and HCl in stock solution were 13.4×10^{-3} and 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ respectively.

A thermostatic water-bath was used to maintain the desired temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reactions were initiated by addition of NBS solution to other reagents. The progress of reaction was followed by determining NBS iodometrically at regular time intervals. The iodine liberated by iridium trichloride was taken into consideration.

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